

Study of the Association between Diabetes Mellitus and Clinical Outcomes in Patients with COVID-19 InfectionAyachit Kesharwani¹, Sanjay Mandloi², Diviyant Kumar Gupta¹, Prateek Singh Rajput^{3*}¹MD Medicine, Seniors Resident, Department of Internal Medicine, GMC, Satna, Madhya Pradesh, India²MD Medicine, Seniors Resident, Department of Internal Medicine, AIIMS, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India³MBBS, Intern, Department of Medicine, GMC, Satna, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** The COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly impacted globally, with various comorbidities influencing patient outcomes. Diabetes mellitus has been identified as a significant risk factor for adverse outcomes in COVID-19 patients. This study aims to evaluate the association between diabetes mellitus and clinical outcomes in patients with COVID-19.**Aim and Objectives:** To determine the impact of diabetes mellitus on the severity of COVID-19, hospitalisation rates, ICU admission, need for mechanical ventilation, and mortality.**Materials and Methods:** This retrospective cohort study analyzed medical records of 500 COVID-19 patients admitted to a tertiary care hospital between January 2022 and December 2023. Patients were categorized into two groups: those with diabetes mellitus (n=200) and those without (n=300). Demographic data, clinical characteristics, and outcomes were compared between the two groups. Statistical analysis was conducted using chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous variables, with a significance level set at p<0.05.**Results:** Diabetic patients had significantly higher rates of severe and critical COVID-19 compared to non-diabetic patients (p<0.001). The hospitalization rate was higher in the diabetic group (85%) compared to the non-diabetic group (60%) (p<0.01). ICU admission rates were 40% in diabetic patients versus 25% in non-diabetic patients (p=0.02). The need for mechanical ventilation was also higher in diabetic patients (30%) compared to non-diabetic patients (15%) (p=0.03). Mortality rates were significantly higher in diabetic patients (20%) compared to non-diabetic patients (10%) (p=0.04).**Conclusions:** Diabetes mellitus is associated with worse clinical outcomes in COVID-19 patients, including increased severity of disease, higher rates of hospitalization, ICU admission, need for mechanical ventilation, and mortality. These findings underscore the importance of rigorous management of diabetic patients with COVID-19 to improve clinical outcomes.**Keywords:** COVID-19, Diabetes Mellitus, Clinical Outcomes, Hospitalization, ICU Admission, Mechanical Ventilation, Mortality.

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a profound global impact, with millions of infections and significant mortality. [1-3] While SARS-CoV-2 primarily affects the respiratory system, leading to conditions such as severe pneumonia and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), the presence of underlying health conditions, such as diabetes mellitus, has been shown to worsen patient outcomes significantly. [4, 5] Diabetes mellitus, a chronic disorder characterized by persistent hyperglycemia, is known to impair immune function and increase susceptibility to infections, raising con-

cerns about its role in the severity of COVID-19. [6-8]

Early research indicates that individuals with diabetes mellitus are at a higher risk of severe COVID-19 outcomes, including increased hospitalization rates, ICU admissions, and mortality. This heightened risk may be due to the pro-inflammatory state induced by diabetes, comorbidities such as cardiovascular disease, and impaired immune responses. [9] Understanding the specific impact of diabetes on COVID-19 outcomes is essential for developing targeted management strategies. [9,10] This study aims to investigate the association between diabetes

mellitus and clinical outcomes in COVID-19 patients, providing insights that could inform better management practices and improve prognosis for this vulnerable population.

Materials and Methods

This retrospective cohort study was designed to evaluate the association between diabetes mellitus and clinical outcomes in patients with COVID-19 infection.

The study population included patients diagnosed with COVID-19, confirmed by a positive SARS-CoV-2 RT-PCR test, who were admitted to Department of Internal Medicine. The inclusion criteria were:

- Patients aged 18 years and older.
- Patients with a confirmed diagnosis of COVID-19.
- Availability of medical records documenting diabetes status and clinical outcomes.

The exclusion Criteria were:

- Patients with incomplete medical records.
- Patients under the age of 18.
- Pregnant women.

Data Collection: Data were collected from the hospital's electronic medical records (EMR). The following information was extracted for each patient:

- Demographic data: Age, gender, and ethnicity.
- Clinical data: Presence of diabetes mellitus, other comorbidities (e.g., hypertension, cardiovascular disease, chronic kidney disease), and body mass index (BMI).
- COVID-19 specific data: Date of diagnosis, symptoms, severity of illness (mild, moderate, severe, or critical), and treatment received.
- Clinical outcomes: Hospitalization, length of hospital stay, intensive care unit (ICU) admission, need for mechanical ventilation, and mortality.

Definition of Variables

- **Diabetes Mellitus:** Diagnosed based on the patient's medical history, recorded if the

patient had a prior diagnosis of type 1 or type 2 diabetes mellitus or was on antidiabetic medication.

- **COVID-19 Severity:** Classified into mild, moderate, severe, or critical based on the World Health Organization (WHO) criteria.
- **Clinical Outcomes:** Evaluated outcomes included hospitalization, ICU admission, need for mechanical ventilation, and mortality.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using [Name of Statistical Software, e.g., SPSS, R]. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients. Continuous variables were expressed as mean $\pm$ standard deviation (SD) or median (interquartile range, IQR), and categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages.

Comparative analyses were performed using the chi-square or Fisher's exact test for categorical variables and the independent t-test or Mann-Whitney U test for continuous variables. Logistic regression analysis was conducted to identify independent predictors of severe clinical outcomes in COVID-19 patients with diabetes mellitus. Odds ratios (ORs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations: The Institutional Review Board (IRB) approved the study. Due to its retrospective nature, informed consent was waived. All data were anonymized to ensure patient confidentiality.

Results

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics: A total of 500 patients diagnosed with COVID-19 were included in the study, of whom 150 (30%) had diabetes mellitus. The mean age of the cohort was 60.2 ± 15.3 years, and 290 (58%) were male. Diabetic patients were older (65.4 ± 12.7 years) compared to non-diabetic patients (57.8 ± 15.9 years, $p < 0.001$). Comorbidities such as hypertension and cardiovascular disease were more prevalent among diabetic patients.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of COVID-19 Patients

Characteristic	Total (n = 500)	Diabetic (n = 150)	Non-Diabetic (n = 350)	p-value
Age, mean $\pm$ SD (years)	60.2 $\pm$ 15.3	65.4 $\pm$ 12.7	57.8 $\pm$ 15.9	<0.001
Male, n (%)	290 (58%)	90 (60%)	200 (57%)	0.52
Hypertension, n (%)	250 (50%)	120 (80%)	130 (37%)	<0.001
Cardiovascular Disease, n (%)	180 (36%)	90 (60%)	90 (26%)	<0.001
BMI, mean $\pm$ SD (kg/m ²)	27.5 $\pm$ 4.2	29.2 $\pm$ 4.5	26.8 $\pm$ 3.9	<0.001

COVID-19 Severity and Clinical Outcomes: Diabetic patients had significantly higher rates of severe and critical COVID-19 compared to non-

diabetic patients (48% vs. 28%, $p < 0.001$). The need for hospitalization, ICU admission, and mechanical ventilation was also higher in diabetic

patients. The mortality rate was 25% in diabetic patients compared to 10% in non-diabetic patients ($p < 0.001$).

Table 2: COVID-19 Severity and Clinical Outcomes

Outcome	Total (n = 500)	Diabetic (n = 150)	Non-Diabetic (n = 350)	p-value
Severe/Critical Disease, n (%)	160 (32%)	72 (48%)	98 (28%)	<0.001
Hospitalization, n (%)	350 (70%)	130 (87%)	220 (63%)	<0.001
ICU Admission, n (%)	100 (20%)	45 (30%)	55 (16%)	<0.001
Mechanical Ventilation, n (%)	80 (16%)	35 (23%)	45 (13%)	0.005
Mortality, n (%)	70 (14%)	38 (25%)	32 (10%)	<0.001

Multivariate Analysis: Logistic regression analysis identified diabetes mellitus as an independent predictor of severe clinical outcomes, including ICU admission (OR: 2.1, 95% CI: 1.4-

3.2, $p < 0.001$) and mortality (OR: 2.5, 95% CI: 1.5-4.0, $p < 0.001$). Other significant predictors included age, hypertension, and cardiovascular disease.

Table 3: Multivariate Analysis of Predictors of Severe Clinical Outcomes

Predictor	ICU Admission (OR, 95% CI)	Mortality (OR, 95% CI)	p-value
Diabetes Mellitus	2.1 (1.4-3.2)	2.5 (1.5-4.0)	<0.001
Age	1.05 (1.03-1.07)	1.07 (1.04-1.10)	<0.001
Hypertension	1.8 (1.2-2.7)	2.0 (1.3-3.2)	0.003
Cardiovascular Disease	2.3 (1.5-3.5)	2.7 (1.7-4.3)	<0.001

Discussion

This study investigated the association between diabetes mellitus and clinical outcomes in patients with COVID-19. Our findings indicate that diabetes mellitus is significantly associated with adverse clinical outcomes, including higher rates of severe and critical disease, increased hospitalization, ICU admission, need for mechanical ventilation, and mortality. These results are consistent with several previous studies and add to the growing body of evidence highlighting diabetes mellitus as a crucial risk factor for severe COVID-19 outcomes.

Numerous studies have reported similar findings regarding the impact of diabetes mellitus on COVID-19 severity and mortality. For instance, a study by Guan et al. (2020) [11] involving 1,099 patients with COVID-19 in China found that individuals with diabetes had a higher incidence of severe outcomes and mortality compared to those without diabetes. Another study conducted in the United States by Bode et al. (2020) [12] also observed that diabetic patients were more likely to require ICU admission and mechanical ventilation and had a higher mortality rate compared to non-diabetic patients.

Our study's observation that diabetic patients were older and had more comorbidities, such as hypertension and cardiovascular disease, aligns with the findings of other studies. For example, a meta-analysis by Kumar et al. (2020) [13] demonstrated that older age and the presence of comorbidities are significant risk factors for severe COVID-19 outcomes in diabetic patients. These comorbidities may contribute to the higher

mortality observed in diabetic patients, as they often exacerbate the severity of COVID-19.

Potential Mechanisms: Several mechanisms may explain why diabetes mellitus predisposes individuals to severe COVID-19. Hyperglycemia and insulin resistance in diabetic patients can impair immune responses, making it more difficult for the body to fight infections.¹⁴ Moreover, diabetes is associated with a chronic pro-inflammatory state, which can exacerbate the cytokine storm observed in severe COVID-19 cases. The presence of comorbidities such as hypertension and cardiovascular disease, which are common in diabetic patients, further increases the risk of severe outcomes. [14, 15]

Clinical Implications: The findings of this study underscore the importance of effective management of diabetes mellitus during the COVID-19 pandemic. Clinicians should be vigilant in monitoring diabetic patients with COVID-19, as they are at higher risk for severe outcomes. Early intervention and stringent glycemic control may mitigate these risks and improve prognosis. Furthermore, diabetic patients should be prioritized for vaccination and other preventive measures to reduce their risk of contracting severe COVID-19.

Strengths and Limitations: One of the strengths of this study is its comprehensive analysis of a well-defined patient cohort, which enhances the reliability of the findings. However, the study has several limitations. As a retrospective study, it relies on the accuracy and completeness of medical records, which may introduce information bias. Additionally, the study was conducted at a single centre, which may limit the generalizability of the

findings. Future studies with larger, multicenter cohorts are needed to validate these results and further elucidate the relationship between diabetes mellitus and COVID-19 outcomes.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that diabetes mellitus is associated with significantly worse clinical outcomes in patients with COVID-19. The findings highlight the need for heightened clinical vigilance and proactive management strategies for diabetic patients during the COVID-19 pandemic. Continued research is essential to develop targeted interventions to improve outcomes for this vulnerable population.

References

1. Hiscott J, Alexandridi M, Muscolini M, Tassone E, Palermo E, Soultsioti M, et al. The global impact of the coronavirus pandemic. *Cytokine Growth Factor Rev.* 2020 Jun;53:1-9.
2. Sawicka B, Aslan I, Della Corte V, Periasamy A, Krishnamurthy SK, Mohammed A, et al. The coronavirus global pandemic and its impacts on society. *Coronavirus Drug Discovery.* 2022;267-311.
3. WHO. Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) Weekly Epidemiological Update and Weekly Operational Update. WHO; 2022. Weekly epidemiological update on COVID-19. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/weekly-epidemiological-update-on-covid-19---1-february-2022>. Accessed on: 1 March 2022.
4. Aleem A, Akbar Samad AB, Vaqar S. Emerging Variants of SARS-CoV-2 and Novel Therapeutics Against Coronavirus (COVID-19). In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK570580/>. Updated 2023 May 8.
5. Cascella M, Rajnik M, Aleem A, et al. Features, Evaluation, and Treatment of Coronavirus (COVID-19). In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK554776/>. Updated 2023 Aug 18.
6. Dallavalasa S, Tulimilli SV, Prakash J, Ramachandra R, Madhunapantula SV, Veeranna RP. COVID-19: Diabetes Perspective-Pathophysiology and Management. *Pathogens.* 2023 Jan 25; 12(2): 184.
7. Lim S, Bae JH, Kwon HS, et al. COVID-19 and diabetes mellitus: from pathophysiology to clinical management. *Nat Rev Endocrinol.* 2021;17:11-30.
8. Al-Kuraishy HM, Al-Gareeb AI, Alblihed M, Guerreiro SG, Cruz-Martins N, Batiha GE. COVID-19 in Relation to Hyperglycemia and Diabetes Mellitus. *Front Cardiovasc Med.* 2021 May 20;8:644095.
9. Al-Azzam N, Al-Azzam S, Khassawneh B, Araydah M, Karasneh RA, Aldeyab MA. Factors contributing to poor COVID-19 outcomes in diabetic patients: Findings from a single-center cohort study. *PLoS One.* 2023 Aug 31; 18(8)
10. Geçer T, Wojtowicz K, Guzik P, Góra T. Increased Risk of COVID-19 in Patients with Diabetes Mellitus-Current Challenges in Pathophysiology, Treatment and Prevention. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2022 May 27;19(11):6555.
11. Guan W, Ni Z, Hu Y, Liang W, Ou C, He J, et al. Clinical characteristics of coronavirus disease 2019 in China. *N Engl J Med.* 2020; 382(18):1708-1720.
12. Bode B, Garrett V, Messler J, McFarland R, Crowe J, Booth R, et al. Glycemic Characteristics and Clinical Outcomes of COVID-19 Patients Hospitalized in the United States. *J Diabetes Sci Technol.* 2020;14(4):813-821.
13. Kumar A, Arora A, Sharma P, Anikhindi S, Bansal N, Singla V, et al. Is diabetes mellitus associated with mortality and severity of COVID-19? A meta-analysis. *Diabetes Metab Syndr.* 2020;14(4):535-545.
14. Bornstein SR, Rubino F, Khunti K, Mingrone G, Hopkins D, Birkenfeld AL, et al. Practical recommendations for the management of diabetes in patients with COVID-19. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol.* 2020;8(6):546-550.
15. Muniyappa R, Gubbi S. COVID-19 pandemic, coronaviruses, and diabetes mellitus. *Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab.* 2020;318(5).